

A STUDY OF LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR OF HIGHER SECONDARY TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to investigate the leadership behaviours of higher secondary teachers. The research analysis was descriptive and differential. A sample size of 429 higher secondary teachers was simply selected randomly by proportional sampling. For data collection, Leadership Behaviour tool constructed and validated by Mary. K.A and Jai Prasad A.T (2009) was used. To analyze the data, mean, standard deviation, t-test and one-way ANOVA were used. An inventory questions was used to get qualitative data. Participants were 429 higher secondary teachers (272 females, 157 males) from a Vellore city in Tamilnadu. Results of this study concluded that a significant difference between of higher secondary teachers towards members in social club and further the study revealed that there is no significant difference between of higher secondary teachers towards gender, status, location of school, mode of management, residence, nature of school, teaching experience, in service training, marital status and type of family.

Introduction:

Educational institutions are critical places where the next generation is educated, and school leaders bear a heavy burden of responsibility for their institutions. Leaders in educational institutions are the same as leaders in other organizations, and inevitably face the challenge of maintaining the goals of the institutions. (North house, 2010). According to Kenneth, Frank and Peter (2014). Head teachers' leadership behavior is described in terms of two broad behaviour patterns, one concern with establishing an attitude of warmth and respect with teachers (concern for people or consideration) and two, organizing and defining the tasks of teachers in relation to goals (concern for tasks or initiating structure).

Leadership behavior is the main factor that greatly influences school effectiveness and should not be underscored. Most school heads are not effective in their leadership behavior because they treat teachers as tools believing that teachers can be treated anyhow. In response to this, teachers do not handle their work properly. In highly effective schools, and schools which have reserved a trend of poor performance and declining achievements, the head teacher sets the pace leading and motivating pupils and staff to perform to their highest potential (Bush and Oduro, 2006).

Significance of the Problem:

Leadership is defined in terms of qualities interaction or an aspect of organization where the scope of action from individual is defined in making decisions and parenting pattern is a term that summarizes behaviours used by mother or father to raise the child. Man is a social animal. He lives in a society and acquires socialization and fulfills his psychological and sociological needs. His personality develops in the society due to impact of his environment. But we usually see that parents emphasize great impact on the personality of the child. It is reality that the child develops in social atmosphere but basically he acquires qualities from parental pattern.

Education is a central agency in shaping the future of the individual and the nation. The quality of citizen depends upon the education that is imparted to them. It has been a vital force in regeneration of nation. The quality of education that goes in the schools is directly proportional to organizational climate, leadership and organizational practices. Every school has its personality in the sense of its unique characteristics by which it is marked and singled out from all other school and this intangible factor within the school determines the leadership qualities within the school. Leadership behaviour gets its final shape during school life. Hence it is necessary to study the leadership qualities of teachers in context of working life or area in which they work. Moreover co-curricular activities help to inculcate the quality of leadership. Co-curricular activities helps in physical development, Sublimation of instincts, inculcate moral values, civics values and refining the social values. We can utilize our leisure time by participating in Co-curricular activities.

Statement of the Problem:

Much has been written about leadership behavior in education. The vast majority of that literature refers to teachers from primary, secondary, higher secondary and higher institution. However, little systematic research has been conducted regarding nursery school teachers. Nursery school teachers have unique characteristics which differentiate them from other educators, for example, nursery school teachers have to teach in indoors classroom as well as outdoors. They are expected to be emotionally available and to expand a lot of energy for a long period of time. This study would bring to fore portable underlying influence of school teacher

behavior and its impact on some unethical behavior of teachers working in higher secondary towards leadership behavior.

Operational Definition of Term Used Leadership Behaviour:

Leadership behaviour we mean the particular acts in which a leader engages in the course of directing and coordinating the work of his group members and showing consideration for their welfare and feeling during working life.

Methodology:

Sampling Technique:

The simple random sampling technique was used by the researcher to collect the data. The researcher collected the data randomly from Government, Aided and Private schools based on higher secondary teachers from Vellore district of Tamilnadu.

Sampling Area:

The sample was taken from Government / Aided and Private higher secondary schools of Vellore district districts of Tamilnadu.

Description of the Leadership Behaviour Inventory:

To find the leadership behaviour, the investigator has used the tool constructed and validated by Mary. K.A and Jai Prasadh A.T (2009). The tool contains 36 statements whose response can be used to measure the individual behaviour as a teacher. Each statement has to be answered by choosing any one of the alternatives such as Strongly agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly disagree. Scoring ranges form 5,4,3,2 and 1.

Statistical Techniques:

The following statistical techniques would be employed to test the hypothesis of the present study.

- ✓ Mean
- ✓ Standard deviation
- ✓ t test
- ✓ F test.

Data Analysis:

The data collected from the sample population were systematically coded, tabulated and organized for analysis. The coded data were entered in to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. In addition, t-test and F test was used to see if there is statistically significant difference between teachers actual and desired level of participation in leadership behavior.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out the significant difference if any between the following higher secondary Teacher in respect of their leadership behavior

- ✓ Gender : Male / Female
- ✓ Status : Temporary / Permanent
- ✓ Location of school : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Mode of management : Government / Private / Aided
- ✓ Residence : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Nature of school : Boys / Girls / Co education
- ✓ Teaching experience : Below 5 years / 6-10 years / 11-15 years / Above 16 years
- ✓ In-service training : Attended / Not attended
- ✓ Member in social club : Yes / No
- ✓ Marital status : Married / Unmarried
- ✓ Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

Hypotheses of the Study:

There is no significant difference in if any between the following higher secondary Teacher in respect of their leadership behavior

- ✓ Gender : Male / Female
- ✓ Status : Temporary / Permanent
- ✓ Location of school : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Mode of management : Government / Private / Aided
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- ✓ In-service training : Attended / Not attended
- ✓ Member in social club : Yes / No
- ✓ Marital status : Married / Unmarried
- ✓ Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Difference between Male and Female Higher Secondary Teachers in Their Leadership Behaviour

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Male	157	149.10	13.5	0.741	NS
Female	257	148.10	13.4		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 2: Difference between Permanent and Temporary Higher Secondary Teachers in their Leadership Behaviour

Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Permanent	318	148.64	13.629	0.47	NS
Temporary	111	147.95	13.031		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between permanent and temporary higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 3: Difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Teachers in Their Leadership Behaviour

Location of School	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Rural	237	148.23	12.168	0.391	NS
Urban	192	148.75	14.939		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between rural and urban location of school of higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 4: Difference among Government, Aided and Private Higher Secondary Teachers in Their Leadership Behaviour

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'-value	Remarks
Between	300.720	150.360	0.829	NS
Within	77297.895	181.450		

(At 5% level of significance for 2,426 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among government, aided and private higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 5: Difference between Rural and Urban Residence of Higher Secondary Teachers in their Leadership Behaviour

Residence	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Rural	269	148.47	13.051	0.013	NS
Urban	160	148.45	14.175		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between residence of rural and urban higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 6: Difference Among Boys', Girls' and Co-Education School Higher Secondary Teachers in Their Leadership Behaviour

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'-value	Remarks
Between	176.737	88.369	0.486	NS
Within	77421.878	181.741		

(At 5% level of significance for 2,426 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among boys', girls' and co-education higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 7: Difference Among Higher Secondary Teachers of Below 5 Years, 6 to 10 Years, 11 to 15 Years and Above 16 Years of Experience in their Leadership Behaviour

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'-value	Remarks
Between	462.609	154.203	0.850	NS
Within	77136.006	181.496		

(At 5% level of significance for 3,425 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among the higher secondary teachers having teaching experience below 5 years, 6 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years and above 16 years in their leadership behaviour.

Table 8: Difference between Higher Secondary Teachers Who Attended and Not-Attended In-Service Training in Their Leadership Behaviour

In-service Training	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Attended	291	147.93	13.766	1.21	NS
Not attended	138	149.58	12.783		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between higher secondary teachers who attended and not attended in-service training in their leadership behaviour.

Table 9: Difference between Members and Non-Members of Social Clubs of Higher Secondary Teachers in Their Leadership Behaviour

Members in social club	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Yes	145	150.43	12.699	2.23	S
No	284	147.45	13.752		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference between members and non-members in social clubs of higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 10: Difference between Married and Unmarried Higher Secondary Teachers in their Leadership Behaviour

Marital Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Married	350	148.66	13.439	0.627	NS
Unmarried	79	147.59	13.631		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between married and unmarried higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Table 11: Difference between Nuclear and Joint Family Higher Secondary Teachers in their Leadership Behaviour

Family Type	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Nuclear	261	147.91	13.482	1.054	NS
Joint	168	149.32	13.433		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family of higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between permanent and temporary higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between rural and urban location of school of higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference among government, aided and private higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between residence of rural and urban higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference among boys', girls' and co-education higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference among the higher secondary teachers having teaching experience below 5 years, 6 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years and above 16 years in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that that there is no significant difference between higher secondary teachers who attended and not attended in-service training in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is significant difference between members and non-members in social clubs of higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between married and unmarried higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family of higher secondary teachers in their leadership behaviour.

Conclusion and Recommendation:

This study had amply revealed that higher secondary teachers in Vellore District in Tamil nadu state, where exhibited positive leadership behavior. For example being friendly and fairness in judgment. The result also showed that teachers in the visited were satisfied with their jobs. It is therefore recommended that a similar study should be carried out in other states of federation. Such a study may investigate the leadership behavior of male and female head teachers in the higher secondary schools. This study also recommends that school teacher should imbibe positive leadership behavior like being supportive, kind and fair. The teachers of schools should ensure that teachers are not dissatisfied with their jobs through their inability to provide enabling environment and adequate incentives.

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